

Interval Valued Neutrosophic Fuzzy Ideals of Near-Rings

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Abstract

This paper serves as an introduction to the idea of subnear-rings in the context of interval valued neutrosophic fuzzy sets and explores their relationship with ideals within near-rings. The focus lies in the characterization of various algebraic properties, including but not limited to the union, intersection, and direct product of interval valued neutrosophic fuzzy ideals within near-rings.

Keywords: Near-rings; neutrosophic fuzzy set; interval valued neutrosophic fuzzy ideals.

1. Introduction

The foundational idea of fuzzy sets was initially proposed by L.A. Zadeh in 1965[16]. Later, in 1975, Zadeh extended this concept to introduce interval-valued (i-v) fuzzy subsets, where membership function values are represented as closed interval numbers rather than single values[17]. In 1991, S. Abou-Zaid introduced fuzzy subnear-rings and fuzzy ideals of near-rings[1], while B. Davvaz, in 2001, introduced fuzzy ideals and near-rings with i-v membership functions[5]. Y.B. Jun and K.H. Kim applied concepts of i-v fuzzy R-subgroup and ideals in near rings in 2002[6], and in the 2016, N. Thillaigovindan et al. introduced the notion of i-v anti fuzzy ideals of near-rings[15]. K. Lenin Muthu Kumaran, S. Selvaraj (2023), discussed about interval valued neutrosophic fuzzy ideals in semigroups [8]. The concept of neutrosophy, introduced by Florentin Smarandache in 2002, represents a branch of philosophy that extends fuzzy logic to include indeterminacy[11]. Notably, neutrosophic logic assigns a percentage of truth [in subset T], indeterminacy [in subset I], and falsity [in subset F] to each proposition. Neutrosophic set theory has found success in various fields, including medical diagnosis, image processing, decision-making, and robotics. Section 2 of this paper provides essential definitions of near-rings and ideals. Section 3 explores the concept of i-v neutrosophic fuzzy structures, encompassing i-v neutrosophic fuzzy near-rings, subnear-rings, and left (resp. right) ideals within near-rings, along with an analysis of their algebraic properties. Finally, section 4 summarizes key findings and outlines directions for future research.

2. Preliminaries

Within this segment, we enumerate fundamental principles of i-v fuzzy set theory. Throughout this paper R will denote a left near-ring.

Definition 2.1 [7]

A non empty set R , with two binary operations, denoted as '+' and '·', it is called a near-ring.

- 1) $(R, +)$ is a group
- 2) $(R, \cdot)$ is a semigroup
- 3) $u \cdot (v + w) = u \cdot v + u \cdot w$ for all $u, v, w \in R$

When we refer to a 'left near-ring', we use the term 'near-ring'. Additionally, we represent the product of u and v as uv instead of $u \cdot v$. Note that $u0 = 0$ and $u(-v) = -uv$, but in general $0u \neq 0$ for some $u \in R$.

Definition 2.2 [7]

An ideal I , of a near-ring R is a subset of R such that

- 1) $(I, +)$ is a normal subgroup of $(R, +)$
- 2) $RI \subseteq I$
- 3) $((u + i)v - uv) \in I$ for any $i \in I$ and $u, v \in R$.

Note that I is a left ideal of R if it satisfies (1) and (2), and I is a right ideal of R if it satisfies (1) and (3).

Definition 2.3 [12]

An i-v number $\bar{n}$ on $[0, 1]$ is called a subinterval of $[0, 1]$ (i.e), $\bar{n} = [n^-, n^+]$ such that $0 \leq n^- \leq n^+ \leq 1$, where n^- and n^+ are the lower and upper limits of $\bar{n}$ respectively. In this notation $\bar{0} = [0, 0]$ and $\bar{1} = [1, 1]$. For any two interval numbers $\bar{n} = [n^-, n^+]$ and $\bar{m} = [m^-, m^+]$ on $[0, 1]$ we define

- 1) $\bar{n} \leq \bar{m} \Leftrightarrow n^- \leq m^-$ and $n^+ \leq m^+$
- 2) $\bar{n} = \bar{m} \Leftrightarrow n^- = m^-$ and $n^+ = m^+$

Definition 2.4 [12]

Consider a non-empty set X . A mapping $\bar{\mu}: X \rightarrow D[0, 1]$ is called an i-v fuzzy subset of X , where $D[0, 1]$ denotes the family of all closed subintervals of $[0, 1]$ and $\bar{\mu}(u) = [\mu^-(u), \mu^+(u)]$, μ^- and μ^+ are fuzzy subsets of X such that $\mu^-(u) \leq \mu^+(u)$ for all $u \in X$. Thus $\bar{\mu}(u)$ is an interval (a closed subset of $[0, 1]$) and not a number from the interval $[0, 1]$ as in the case of a fuzzy set.

Definition 2.5 [13]

An i-v fuzzy subset $\bar{\mu}$ of a near-ring R is called an i-v fuzzy subnear-ring of R if

- 1) $\bar{\mu}(u - v) \geq \min^i\{\bar{\mu}(u), \bar{\mu}(v)\}$
- 2) $\bar{\mu}(uv) \geq \min^i\{\bar{\mu}(u), \bar{\mu}(v)\}$ for all $u, v \in R$.

An i-v fuzzy subset $\bar{\mu}$ of a near-ring R is called an i-v fuzzy ideal of R if $\bar{\mu}$ is an i-v fuzzy subnear-ring of R and

- 3) $\bar{\mu}(v + u - v) \geq \bar{\mu}(u)$
- 4) $\bar{\mu}(uv) \geq \bar{\mu}(v)$
- 5) $\bar{\mu}((u + i)v - uv) \geq \bar{\mu}(i)$ for any $u, v, i \in R$.

Note that $\bar{\mu}$ is an i-v fuzzy left ideal of R if it satisfies (1)(2)(3) and (4), and $\bar{\mu}$ is an i-v fuzzy right ideal of R if it satisfies (1)(2)(3) and (5).

Definition 2.6 [12]

Let I be a subset of a near-ring R . Define a function $\bar{f}_I: R \rightarrow D[0, 1]$ by

$$\bar{f}_I(u) = \begin{cases} \bar{1} & \text{if } u \in I \\ \bar{0} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

for all $u \in R$. Clearly $\bar{f}_I$ is an i-v fuzzy subset of R . $\bar{f}_I$ is called the i-v characteristic function of I .

Definition 2.7 [12]

Let $\bar{\mu}$ be an i-v fuzzy subset of a set X and $[t_1 t_2] \in D[0, 1]$, then the set $\bar{U}(\bar{\mu}: [t_1 t_2]) = \{u \in X | \bar{\mu}(u) \geq [t_1 t_2]\}$ is called the upper level set of $\bar{\mu}$.

Definition 2.8 [12]

Let $\bar{\mu}, \bar{\nu}, \bar{\mu}_i (i \in \Omega)$ be i-v fuzzy subsets of X . The following are defined by

- 1) $\bar{\mu} \leq \bar{\nu} \Leftrightarrow \bar{\mu}(u) \leq \bar{\nu}(u)$
- 2) $\bar{\mu} = \bar{\nu} \Leftrightarrow \bar{\mu}(u) = \bar{\nu}(u)$
- 3) $(\bar{\mu} \cup \bar{\nu})(u) = \max^i\{\bar{\mu}(u), \bar{\nu}(u)\}$
- 4) $(\bar{\mu} \cap \bar{\nu})(u) = \min^i\{\bar{\mu}(u), \bar{\nu}(u)\}$
- 5) $\bigcup_{i \in \Omega} \bar{\mu}_i (u) = \sup^i\{\bar{\mu}_i(u) | i \in \Omega\}$
- 6) $\bigcap_{i \in \Omega} \bar{\mu}_i (u) = \inf^i\{\bar{\mu}_i(u) | i \in \Omega\}$

Where $\sup^i\{\bar{\mu}_i(u) | i \in \Omega\} = [\sup_{i \in \Omega}\{\mu_i^-(u)\}, \sup_{i \in \Omega}\{\mu_i^+(u)\}]$ is the i-v supremum norm and $\inf^i\{\bar{\mu}_i(u) | i \in \Omega\} = [\inf_{i \in \Omega}\{\mu_i^-(u)\}, \inf_{i \in \Omega}\{\mu_i^+(u)\}]$ is the i-v infimum norm.

3. Interval Valued Neutrosophic Fuzzy Ideals of Near-Rings

In this section we introduce the notion of i-v neutrosophic fuzzy subnear-rings and ideals of R . We obtain some characterizations of i-v neutrosophic fuzzy ideals of R .

Definition 3.1

Suppose R is a near-ring. An i-v neutrosophic fuzzy set $\bar{A}$ defined on the universe of discourse a near-ring R is characterized by its truth membership function $T_{\bar{A}}(u)$, an indeterminacy function $I_{\bar{A}}(u)$ and a falsity membership function $F_{\bar{A}}(u)$ expressed as follows:

$$\bar{A} = \{(T_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{A}}(u), F_{\bar{A}}(u)) | u \in R\}.$$

It is also denoted by $\bar{A} = \left\{ \frac{u}{(T_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{A}}(u), F_{\bar{A}}(u))} | u \in R \right\}$. Here, the functions $T_{\bar{A}}, I_{\bar{A}}, F_{\bar{A}} : R \rightarrow D[0, 1]$ and the condition $\bar{0} \leq T_{\bar{A}}(u) + I_{\bar{A}}(u) + F_{\bar{A}}(u) \leq \bar{3}$ holds for all elements $u \in R$.

Definition 3.2

An i-v neutrosophic fuzzy subset $\bar{A}$ of a near-ring R then $\bar{A} = \{(u, T_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{A}}(u), F_{\bar{A}}(u)) | u \in R\}$, is called an i-v neutrosophic fuzzy subnear-ring of R if

- 1) $T_{\bar{A}}(u - v) \geq \min^i\{T_{\bar{A}}(u), T_{\bar{A}}(v)\}$
 $I_{\bar{A}}(u - v) \leq \max^i\{I_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{A}}(v)\}$
 $F_{\bar{A}}(u - v) \leq \max^i\{F_{\bar{A}}(u), F_{\bar{A}}(v)\}$
- 2) $T_{\bar{A}}(uv) \geq \min^i\{T_{\bar{A}}(u), T_{\bar{A}}(v)\}$
 $I_{\bar{A}}(uv) \leq \max^i\{I_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{A}}(v)\}$
 $F_{\bar{A}}(uv) \leq \max^i\{F_{\bar{A}}(u), F_{\bar{A}}(v)\}$

An i-v neutrosophic fuzzy set $\bar{A}$ of a near-ring R , is called an i-v neutrosophic fuzzy ideal of R if $\bar{A}$ is an i-v neutrosophic fuzzy subnear-ring of R and

- 3) $T_{\bar{A}}(v + u - v) \geq T_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{A}}(v + u - v) \leq I_{\bar{A}}(u), F_{\bar{A}}(v + u - v) \leq F_{\bar{A}}(u)$
- 4) $T_{\bar{A}}(uv) \geq T_{\bar{A}}(v), I_{\bar{A}}(uv) \leq I_{\bar{A}}(v), F_{\bar{A}}(uv) \leq F_{\bar{A}}(v)$
- 5) $T_{\bar{A}}((u + i)v - uv) \geq T_{\bar{A}}(i), I_{\bar{A}}((u + i)v - uv) \leq I_{\bar{A}}(i), F_{\bar{A}}((u + i)v - uv) \leq F_{\bar{A}}(i)$

Note that $\bar{A}$ is an i-v neutrosophic fuzzy left ideal of R if it satisfies (1)(2)(3) and (4) and $\bar{A}$ is an i-v neutrosophic fuzzy right ideal of R if it satisfies (1)(2)(3) and (5).

Example 3.3

Consider the set $R = \{e, f, g, h\}$ endowed with two binary operations, defined as follows:

+	e	f	g	h
e	e	f	g	h
f	f	e	h	g
g	g	h	f	e
h	h	g	e	f

·	e	f	g	h
e	e	e	e	e
f	e	e	e	e
g	e	e	e	e
h	e	e	f	f

Then clearly $(R, +, \cdot)$ is a left near-ring.

Define $\bar{A}: R \rightarrow D[0,1]$ by $\frac{e}{[0.7,0.9],[0.1,0.3],[0.2,0.4]}, \frac{f}{[0.5,0.7],[0.4,0.5],[0.4,0.6]}, \frac{g}{[0.3,0.5],[0.6,0.7],[0.6,0.8]}, \frac{h}{[0.3,0.5],[0.6,0.7],[0.6,0.8]}$.

It can be verified that $\bar{A}$ is an i-v neutrosophic fuzzy ideal of R .

Example 3.4

Consider the set $R = \{e, f, g, h\}$ endowed with two binary operations, defined as follows:

+	e	f	g	h
e	e	f	g	h
f	f	e	h	g
g	g	h	f	e
h	h	g	e	f

·	e	f	g	h
e	e	e	e	e
f	e	e	e	e
g	e	e	e	e
h	e	f	g	h

Then clearly $(R, +, \cdot)$ is a left near-ring.. Define $\bar{A}: R \rightarrow D[0,1]$ by $\frac{e}{[0.7,0.9],[0.1,0.3],[0.2,0.4]}, \frac{f}{[0.5,0.7],[0.4,0.5],[0.4,0.6]}, \frac{g}{[0.3,0.5],[0.6,0.7],[0.6,0.8]}, \frac{h}{[0.3,0.5],[0.6,0.7],[0.6,0.8]}$. It can be verified that $\bar{A}$ is an i-v neutrosophic fuzzy left ideal of R , but not an i-v fuzzy right ideal of R . Since,

$$T_{\bar{A}}((g + f)h - gh) < T_{\bar{A}}(f), I_{\bar{A}}((g + f)h - gh) \geq I_{\bar{A}}(f), F_{\bar{A}}((g + f)h - gh) > F_{\bar{A}}(f)$$

Example 3.5

Consider the set $R = \{e, f, g, h\}$ endowed with two binary operations, defined as follows:

+	e	f	g	h
e	e	f	g	h
f	f	e	h	g
g	g	h	f	e
h	h	g	e	f

·	e	f	g	h
e	e	e	e	e
f	e	e	e	e
g	e	e	e	e
h	e	e	f	f

Then clearly $(R, +, \cdot)$ is a left near-ring.

Define $\bar{A}: R \rightarrow D[0,1]$ by $\frac{e}{[0.3,0.5],[0.6,0.7],[0.6,0.8]}, \frac{f}{[0.4,0.5],[0.5,0.7],[0.4,0.6]}, \frac{g}{[0.7,0.9],[0.1,0.3],[0.2,0.4]}, \frac{h}{[0.7,0.9],[0.1,0.3],[0.2,0.4]}$.

It can be verified that $\bar{A}$ is not an i-v neutrosophic fuzzy ideal of R .

Definition 3.6

Let $\bar{A}$ and $\bar{B}$ be i-v neutrosophic fuzzy sets of R . Then,

- 1) $\bar{A} \cup \bar{B} = \{u, T_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}, I_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}, F_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}\}$
 Where, $T_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(u) = \max^i\{T_{\bar{A}}(u), T_{\bar{B}}(u)\}$
 $I_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(u) = \min^i\{I_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{B}}(u)\}$
 $F_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(u) = \min^i\{F_{\bar{A}}(u), F_{\bar{B}}(u)\}$
- 2) $\bar{A} \cap \bar{B} = \{u, T_{\bar{A} \cap \bar{B}}, I_{\bar{A} \cap \bar{B}}, F_{\bar{A} \cap \bar{B}}\}$
 Where, $T_{\bar{A} \cap \bar{B}}(u) = \min^i\{T_{\bar{A}}(u), T_{\bar{B}}(u)\}$
 $I_{\bar{A} \cap \bar{B}}(u) = \max^i\{I_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{B}}(u)\}$
 $F_{\bar{A} \cap \bar{B}}(u) = \max^i\{F_{\bar{A}}(u), F_{\bar{B}}(u)\}$

Proposition 3.7 If an i-v neutrosophic fuzzy subset $\bar{A}$ in R satisfies the condition, $\bar{A}(u) = \bar{A}(v + u - v)$, then , $\bar{A}(u + v) = \bar{A}(v + u)$ where $\bar{A} = \{T_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{A}}(u), F_{\bar{A}}(u) \mid u \in R\}$.

Proof. Let $u, v \in R$. $\bar{A}(u + v) = \bar{A}(v + (u + v) - v) = \bar{A}(v + (v + u) - v) = \bar{A}(v + u)$.

Theorem 3.8 Let $\bar{A}$ and $\bar{B}$ are i-v neutrosophic fuzzy ideals of the near-ring R . If $\bar{A}$ is a subset of $\bar{B}$, then the union of $\bar{A}$ and $\bar{B}$ is an i-v neutrosophic fuzzy ideal of R .

Proof. Let $\bar{A}$ and $\bar{B}$ be i-v neutrosophic fuzzy ideals of the near-ring R . Assume that $u, v, w \in R$. Consider,

$$\begin{aligned}
T_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(u-v) &= \max^i \{T_{\bar{A}}(u-v), T_{\bar{B}}(u-v)\} \\
&\geq \max^i \{\min^i \{T_{\bar{A}}(u), T_{\bar{A}}(v)\}, \min^i \{T_{\bar{B}}(u), T_{\bar{B}}(v)\}\} \\
&= \min^i \{\max^i \{T_{\bar{A}}(u), T_{\bar{B}}(u)\}, \max^i \{T_{\bar{A}}(v), T_{\bar{B}}(v)\}\} \\
&= \min^i \{T_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(u), T_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(v)\} \\
I_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(u-v) &= \min^i \{I_{\bar{A}}(u-v), I_{\bar{B}}(u-v)\} \\
&\leq \min^i \{\max^i \{I_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{A}}(v)\}, \max^i \{I_{\bar{B}}(u), I_{\bar{B}}(v)\}\} \\
&= \max^i \{\min^i \{I_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{B}}(u)\}, \min^i \{I_{\bar{A}}(v), I_{\bar{B}}(v)\}\} \\
&= \max^i \{I_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(u), I_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(v)\} \\
F_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(u-v) &= \min^i \{F_{\bar{A}}(u-v), F_{\bar{B}}(u-v)\} \\
&\leq \min^i \{\max^i \{F_{\bar{A}}(u), F_{\bar{A}}(v)\}, \max^i \{F_{\bar{B}}(u), F_{\bar{B}}(v)\}\} \\
&= \max^i \{\min^i \{F_{\bar{A}}(u), F_{\bar{B}}(u)\}, \min^i \{F_{\bar{A}}(v), F_{\bar{B}}(v)\}\} \\
&= \max^i \{F_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(u), F_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(v)\} \\
T_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(uv) &= \max^i \{T_{\bar{A}}(uv), T_{\bar{B}}(uv)\} \\
&\geq \max^i \{\min^i \{T_{\bar{A}}(u), T_{\bar{A}}(v)\}, \min^i \{T_{\bar{B}}(u), T_{\bar{B}}(v)\}\} \\
&= \min^i \{\max^i \{T_{\bar{A}}(u), T_{\bar{B}}(u)\}, \max^i \{T_{\bar{A}}(v), T_{\bar{B}}(v)\}\} \\
&= \min^i \{T_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(u), T_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(v)\} \\
I_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(uv) &= \min^i \{I_{\bar{A}}(uv), I_{\bar{B}}(uv)\} \\
&\leq \min^i \{\max^i \{I_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{A}}(v)\}, \max^i \{I_{\bar{B}}(u), I_{\bar{B}}(v)\}\} \\
&= \max^i \{\min^i \{I_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{B}}(u)\}, \min^i \{I_{\bar{A}}(v), I_{\bar{B}}(v)\}\} \\
&= \max^i \{I_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(u), I_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(v)\} \\
F_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(uv) &= \min^i \{F_{\bar{A}}(uv), F_{\bar{B}}(uv)\} \\
&\leq \min^i \{\max^i \{F_{\bar{A}}(u), F_{\bar{A}}(v)\}, \max^i \{F_{\bar{B}}(u), F_{\bar{B}}(v)\}\} \\
&= \max^i \{\min^i \{F_{\bar{A}}(u), F_{\bar{B}}(u)\}, \min^i \{F_{\bar{A}}(v), F_{\bar{B}}(v)\}\} \\
&= \max^i \{F_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(u), F_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(v)\} \\
T_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(v+u-v) &= \max^i \{T_{\bar{A}}(v+u-v), T_{\bar{B}}(v+u-v)\} \geq \max^i \{T_{\bar{A}}(u), T_{\bar{B}}(u)\} = T_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(u) \\
I_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(v+u-v) &= \min^i \{I_{\bar{A}}(v+u-v), I_{\bar{B}}(v+u-v)\} \leq \min^i \{I_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{B}}(u)\} = I_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(u) \\
F_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(v+u-v) &= \min^i \{F_{\bar{A}}(v+u-v), F_{\bar{B}}(v+u-v)\} \leq \min^i \{F_{\bar{A}}(u), F_{\bar{B}}(u)\} = F_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(u) \\
T_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(uv) &= \max^i \{T_{\bar{A}}(uv), T_{\bar{B}}(uv)\} \geq \max^i \{T_{\bar{A}}(v), T_{\bar{B}}(v)\} = T_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(v) \\
I_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(uv) &= \min^i \{I_{\bar{A}}(uv), I_{\bar{B}}(uv)\} \leq \min^i \{I_{\bar{A}}(v), I_{\bar{B}}(v)\} = I_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(v) \\
F_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(uv) &= \min^i \{F_{\bar{A}}(uv), F_{\bar{B}}(uv)\} \leq \min^i \{F_{\bar{A}}(v), F_{\bar{B}}(v)\} = F_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(v) \\
T_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}((u+w)v-uv) &= \max^i \{T_{\bar{A}}((u+w)v-uv), T_{\bar{B}}((u+w)v-uv)\} \\
&\geq \max^i \{T_{\bar{A}}(w), T_{\bar{B}}(w)\} = T_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(w) \\
I_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}((u+w)v-uv) &= \min^i \{I_{\bar{A}}((u+w)v-uv), I_{\bar{B}}((u+w)v-uv)\} \\
&\leq \min^i \{I_{\bar{A}}(w), I_{\bar{B}}(w)\} = I_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(w) \\
F_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}((u+w)v-uv) &= \min^i \{F_{\bar{A}}((u+w)v-uv), F_{\bar{B}}((u+w)v-uv)\} \\
&\leq \min^i \{F_{\bar{A}}(w), F_{\bar{B}}(w)\} = F_{\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}}(w)
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\bar{A} \cup \bar{B}$ is an i-v neutrosophic fuzzy ideal of R .

Theorem 3.9 Suppose $\bar{A}$ and $\bar{B}$ are i-v neutrosophic fuzzy ideals of the near-ring R . The intersection of $\bar{A}$ and $\bar{B}$ is an i-v neutrosophic fuzzy ideal of R .

Proof. Let $\bar{A}$ and $\bar{B}$ be i-v neutrosophic fuzzy ideals of the near-ring R . Assume that $u, v, w \in R$. Consider,

$$\begin{aligned}
T_{\bar{A} \cap \bar{B}}(u-v) &= \min^i \{T_{\bar{A}}(u-v), T_{\bar{B}}(u-v)\} \\
&\geq \min^i \{\min^i \{T_{\bar{A}}(u), T_{\bar{A}}(v)\}, \min^i \{T_{\bar{B}}(u), T_{\bar{B}}(v)\}\} \\
&= \min^i \{\min^i \{T_{\bar{A}}(u), T_{\bar{B}}(u)\}, \min^i \{T_{\bar{A}}(v), T_{\bar{B}}(v)\}\} \\
&= \min^i \{T_{\bar{A} \cap \bar{B}}(u), T_{\bar{A} \cap \bar{B}}(v)\} \\
I_{\bar{A} \cap \bar{B}}(u-v) &= \max^i \{I_{\bar{A}}(u-v), I_{\bar{B}}(u-v)\} \\
&\leq \max^i \{\max^i \{I_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{A}}(v)\}, \max^i \{I_{\bar{B}}(u), I_{\bar{B}}(v)\}\} \\
&= \max^i \{\max^i \{I_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{B}}(u)\}, \max^i \{I_{\bar{A}}(v), I_{\bar{B}}(v)\}\} \\
&= \max^i \{I_{\bar{A} \cap \bar{B}}(u), I_{\bar{A} \cap \bar{B}}(v)\} \\
F_{\bar{A} \cap \bar{B}}(u-v) &= \max^i \{F_{\bar{A}}(u-v), F_{\bar{B}}(u-v)\} \\
&\leq \max^i \{\max^i \{F_{\bar{A}}(u), F_{\bar{A}}(v)\}, \max^i \{F_{\bar{B}}(u), F_{\bar{B}}(v)\}\} \\
&= \max^i \{\max^i \{F_{\bar{A}}(u), F_{\bar{B}}(u)\}, \max^i \{F_{\bar{A}}(v), F_{\bar{B}}(v)\}\} \\
&= \max^i \{F_{\bar{A} \cap \bar{B}}(u), F_{\bar{A} \cap \bar{B}}(v)\} \\
T_{\bar{A} \cap \bar{B}}(uv) &= \min^i \{T_{\bar{A}}(uv), T_{\bar{B}}(uv)\} \\
&\geq \min^i \{\min^i \{T_{\bar{A}}(u), T_{\bar{A}}(v)\}, \min^i \{T_{\bar{B}}(u), T_{\bar{B}}(v)\}\} \\
&= \min^i \{\min^i \{T_{\bar{A}}(u), T_{\bar{B}}(u)\}, \min^i \{T_{\bar{A}}(v), T_{\bar{B}}(v)\}\} \\
&= \min^i \{T_{\bar{A} \cap \bar{B}}(u), T_{\bar{A} \cap \bar{B}}(v)\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
I_{\bar{A}\bar{B}}(uv) &= \max^i\{I_{\bar{A}}(uv), I_{\bar{B}}(uv)\} \\
&\leq \max^i[\max^i\{I_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{A}}(v)\}, \max^i\{I_{\bar{B}}(u), I_{\bar{B}}(v)\}] \\
&= \max^i[\max^i\{I_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{B}}(u)\}, \max^i\{I_{\bar{A}}(v), I_{\bar{B}}(v)\}] \\
&= \max^i\{I_{\bar{A}\bar{B}}(u), I_{\bar{A}\bar{B}}(v)\} \\
F_{\bar{A}\bar{B}}(uv) &= \max^i\{F_{\bar{A}}(uv), F_{\bar{B}}(uv)\} \\
&\leq \max^i[\max^i\{F_{\bar{A}}(u), F_{\bar{A}}(v)\}, \max^i\{F_{\bar{B}}(u), F_{\bar{B}}(v)\}] \\
&= \max^i[\max^i\{F_{\bar{A}}(u), F_{\bar{B}}(u)\}, \max^i\{F_{\bar{A}}(v), F_{\bar{B}}(v)\}] \\
&= \max^i\{F_{\bar{A}\bar{B}}(u), F_{\bar{A}\bar{B}}(v)\} \\
T_{\bar{A}\bar{B}}(v+u-v) &= \min^i\{T_{\bar{A}}(v+u-v), T_{\bar{B}}(v+u-v)\} \geq \min^i\{T_{\bar{A}}(u), T_{\bar{B}}(u)\} = T_{\bar{A}\bar{B}}(u) \\
I_{\bar{A}\bar{B}}(v+u-v) &= \max^i\{I_{\bar{A}}(v+u-v), I_{\bar{B}}(v+u-v)\} \leq \max^i\{I_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{B}}(u)\} = I_{\bar{A}\bar{B}}(u) \\
F_{\bar{A}\bar{B}}(v+u-v) &= \max^i\{F_{\bar{A}}(v+u-v), F_{\bar{B}}(v+u-v)\} \leq \max^i\{F_{\bar{A}}(u), F_{\bar{B}}(u)\} = F_{\bar{A}\bar{B}}(u) \\
T_{\bar{A}\bar{B}}(uv) &= \min^i\{T_{\bar{A}}(uv), T_{\bar{B}}(uv)\} \geq \min^i\{T_{\bar{A}}(v), T_{\bar{B}}(v)\} = T_{\bar{A}\bar{B}}(v) \\
I_{\bar{A}\bar{B}}(uv) &= \max^i\{I_{\bar{A}}(uv), I_{\bar{B}}(uv)\} \leq \max^i\{I_{\bar{A}}(v), I_{\bar{B}}(v)\} = I_{\bar{A}\bar{B}}(v) \\
F_{\bar{A}\bar{B}}(uv) &= \max^i\{F_{\bar{A}}(uv), F_{\bar{B}}(uv)\} \leq \max^i\{F_{\bar{A}}(v), F_{\bar{B}}(v)\} = F_{\bar{A}\bar{B}}(v) \\
T_{\bar{A}\bar{B}}((u+w)v-uv) &= \min^i\{T_{\bar{A}}((u+w)v-uv), T_{\bar{B}}((u+w)v-uv)\} \\
&\geq \min^i\{T_{\bar{A}}(w), T_{\bar{B}}(w)\} = T_{\bar{A}\bar{B}}(w) \\
I_{\bar{A}\bar{B}}((u+w)v-uv) &= \max^i\{I_{\bar{A}}((u+w)v-uv), I_{\bar{B}}((u+w)v-uv)\} \\
&\leq \max^i\{I_{\bar{A}}(w), I_{\bar{B}}(w)\} = I_{\bar{A}\bar{B}}(w) \\
F_{\bar{A}\bar{B}}((u+w)v-uv) &= \max^i\{F_{\bar{A}}((u+w)v-uv), F_{\bar{B}}((u+w)v-uv)\} \\
&\leq \max^i\{F_{\bar{A}}(w), F_{\bar{B}}(w)\} = F_{\bar{A}\bar{B}}(w)
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\bar{A} \cap \bar{B}$ is an i-v neutrosophic fuzzy ideal of R .

Corollary 3.10 If $\{\bar{A}_i \mid i \in \Omega\}$ is a family of i-v neutrosophic fuzzy ideals of a near-ring R , then the $\bigcap_{i \in \Omega} \bar{A}_i$ is also an i-v neutrosophic fuzzy ideal of the near-ring R , where Ω is any index set.

Proof. The proof of this corollary follows a similar approach to that of the preceding Theorem 3.9.

Theorem 3.11 Let $\bar{A}$ be an i-v neutrosophic subset of the near-ring R , where $\bar{A} = [A^-, A^+]$. $\bar{A}$ is an i-v neutrosophic fuzzy left (resp. right) ideal of R if and only if A^-, A^+ are neutrosophic fuzzy left (resp. right) ideals of R .

Proof. Assume that $\bar{A}$ is an i-v neutrosophic fuzzy left (resp. right) ideal of the near-ring R . For any $u, v, w \in R$. Consider,

$$\begin{aligned}
[T_{\bar{A}}(u-v), T_{\bar{A}}(u-v)] &= T_{\bar{A}}(u-v) \geq \min^i\{T_{\bar{A}}(u), T_{\bar{A}}(v)\} \\
&= \min^i\{[T_{A^-}(u), T_{A^+}(u)], [T_{A^-}(v), T_{A^+}(v)]\} \\
&= [\min^i\{T_{A^-}(u), T_{A^-}(v)\}, \min^i\{T_{A^+}(u), T_{A^+}(v)\}]
\end{aligned}$$

As a consequently, $T_{\bar{A}}(u-v) \geq \min^i\{T_{\bar{A}}(u), T_{\bar{A}}(v)\}$ and $T_{\bar{A}}(u-v) = \min^i\{T_{\bar{A}}(u), T_{\bar{A}}(v)\}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
[I_{\bar{A}}(u-v), I_{\bar{A}}(u-v)] &= I_{\bar{A}}(u-v) \leq \max^i\{I_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{A}}(v)\} \\
&= \max^i\{[I_{A^-}(u), I_{A^+}(u)], [I_{A^-}(v), I_{A^+}(v)]\} \\
&= [\max^i\{I_{A^-}(u), I_{A^-}(v)\}, \max^i\{I_{A^+}(u), I_{A^+}(v)\}]
\end{aligned}$$

As a consequently, $I_{\bar{A}}(u-v) \geq \max^i\{I_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{A}}(v)\}$ and $I_{\bar{A}}(u-v) = \max^i\{I_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{A}}(v)\}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
[F_{\bar{A}}(u-v), F_{\bar{A}}(u-v)] &= F_{\bar{A}}(u-v) \leq \max^i\{F_{\bar{A}}(u), F_{\bar{A}}(v)\} \\
&= \max^i\{[F_{A^-}(u), F_{A^+}(u)], [F_{A^-}(v), F_{A^+}(v)]\} \\
&= [\max^i\{F_{A^-}(u), F_{A^-}(v)\}, \max^i\{F_{A^+}(u), F_{A^+}(v)\}]
\end{aligned}$$

As a consequently, $F_{\bar{A}}(u-v) \geq \max^i\{F_{\bar{A}}(u), F_{\bar{A}}(v)\}$ and $F_{\bar{A}}(u-v) = \max^i\{F_{\bar{A}}(u), F_{\bar{A}}(v)\}$.

$$\begin{aligned}
[T_{\bar{A}}(uv), T_{\bar{A}}(uv)] &= T_{\bar{A}}(uv) \geq \min^i\{T_{\bar{A}}(u), T_{\bar{A}}(v)\} \\
&= \min^i\{[T_{A^-}(u), T_{A^+}(u)], [T_{A^-}(v), T_{A^+}(v)]\} \\
&= [\min^i\{T_{A^-}(u), T_{A^-}(v)\}, \min^i\{T_{A^+}(u), T_{A^+}(v)\}]
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, $T_{\bar{A}}(uv) \geq \min^i\{T_{\bar{A}}(u), T_{\bar{A}}(v)\}$ and $T_{\bar{A}}(uv) = \min^i\{T_{\bar{A}}(u), T_{\bar{A}}(v)\}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
[I_{\bar{A}}(uv), I_{\bar{A}}(uv)] &= I_{\bar{A}}(uv) \leq \max^i\{I_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{A}}(v)\} \\
&= \max^i\{[I_{A^-}(u), I_{A^+}(u)], [I_{A^-}(v), I_{A^+}(v)]\} \\
&= [\max^i\{I_{A^-}(u), I_{A^-}(v)\}, \max^i\{I_{A^+}(u), I_{A^+}(v)\}]
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, $I_{\bar{A}}(uv) \geq \max^i\{I_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{A}}(v)\}$ and $I_{\bar{A}}(uv) = \max^i\{I_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{A}}(v)\}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
[F_{\bar{A}}(uv), F_{\bar{A}}(uv)] &= F_{\bar{A}}(uv) \leq \max^i\{F_{\bar{A}}(u), F_{\bar{A}}(v)\} \\
&= \max^i\{[F_{A^-}(u), F_{A^+}(u)], [F_{A^-}(v), F_{A^+}(v)]\} \\
&= [\max^i\{F_{A^-}(u), F_{A^-}(v)\}, \max^i\{F_{A^+}(u), F_{A^+}(v)\}]
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, $F_{\bar{A}}(uv) \geq \max^i\{F_{\bar{A}}(u), F_{\bar{A}}(v)\}$ and $F_{\bar{A}}(uv) = \max^i\{F_{\bar{A}}(u), F_{\bar{A}}(v)\}$.

$$[T_{\bar{A}}(v+u-v), T_{\bar{A}}(v+u-v)] = T_{\bar{A}}(v+u-v) \geq T_{\bar{A}}(u) = [T_{\bar{A}}(u), T_{\bar{A}}(u)]$$

It follows that $T_{\bar{A}}(v+u-v) = T_{\bar{A}}(u)$ and $T_{\bar{A}}(v+u-v) = T_{\bar{A}}(u)$,

$$[I_{\bar{A}}(v+u-v), I_{\bar{A}}(v+u-v)] = I_{\bar{A}}(v+u-v) \leq I_{\bar{A}}(u) = [I_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{A}}(u)]$$

It follows that $I_{A^-}(v + u - v) = I_{A^-}(u)$ and $I_{A^+}(v + u - v) = I_{A^+}(u)$,
 $[F_{A^-}(v + u - v), F_{A^+}(v + u - v)] = F_{\bar{A}}(v + u - v) \leq F_{\bar{A}}(u) = [F_{A^-}(u), F_{A^+}(u)]$
 It follows that $F_{A^-}(v + u - v) = F_{A^-}(u)$ and $F_{A^+}(v + u - v) = F_{A^+}(u)$.
 $[T_{A^-}(uv), T_{A^+}(uv)] = T_{\bar{A}}(uv) \geq T_{\bar{A}}(v) = [T_{A^-}(v), T_{A^+}(v)]$
 As a result $T_{A^-}(uv) = T_{A^-}(v)$ and $T_{A^+}(uv) = T_{A^+}(v)$,
 $[I_{A^-}(uv), I_{A^+}(uv)] = I_{\bar{A}}(uv) \leq I_{\bar{A}}(v) = [I_{A^-}(v), I_{A^+}(v)]$
 As a result $I_{A^-}(uv) = I_{A^-}(v)$ and $I_{A^+}(uv) = I_{A^+}(v)$,
 $[F_{A^-}(uv), F_{A^+}(uv)] = F_{\bar{A}}(uv) \leq F_{\bar{A}}(v) = [F_{A^-}(v), F_{A^+}(v)]$
 As a result $F_{A^-}(uv) = F_{A^-}(v)$ and $F_{A^+}(uv) = F_{A^+}(v)$.
 $[T_{A^-}((u + w)v - uv), T_{A^+}((u + w)v - uv)] = T_{\bar{A}}((u + w)v - uv) \geq T_{\bar{A}}(w) = [T_{A^-}(w), T_{A^+}(w)]$
 As a consequently $T_{A^-}((u + w)v - uv) = T_{A^-}(w)$ and $T_{A^+}((u + w)v - uv) = T_{A^+}(w)$,
 $[I_{A^-}((u + w)v - uv), I_{A^+}((u + w)v - uv)] = I_{\bar{A}}((u + w)v - uv) \leq I_{\bar{A}}(w) = [I_{A^-}(w), I_{A^+}(w)]$
 As a consequently $I_{A^-}((u + w)v - uv) = I_{A^-}(w)$ and $I_{A^+}((u + w)v - uv) = I_{A^+}(w)$,
 $[F_{A^-}((u + w)v - uv), F_{A^+}((u + w)v - uv)] = F_{\bar{A}}((u + w)v - uv) \leq F_{\bar{A}}(w) = [F_{A^-}(w), F_{A^+}(w)]$
 As a consequently $F_{A^-}((u + w)v - uv) = F_{A^-}(w)$ and $F_{A^+}((u + w)v - uv) = F_{A^+}(w)$.
 Conversely, assume that A^-, A^+ are fuzzy left (resp. right) ideals of R .

Let $u, v, w \in R$. Then

$$T_{\bar{A}}(u - v) = [T_{A^-}(u - v), T_{A^+}(u - v)] \geq [\min^i\{T_{A^-}(u), T_{A^-}(v)\}, \min^i\{T_{A^+}(u), T_{A^+}(v)\}]$$

$$= \min^i\{[T_{A^-}(u), T_{A^+}(u)], [T_{A^-}(v), T_{A^+}(v)]\}$$

$$= \min^i\{T_{\bar{A}}(u), T_{\bar{A}}(v)\}$$

$$I_{\bar{A}}(u - v) = [I_{A^-}(u - v), I_{A^+}(u - v)] \leq [\max^i\{I_{A^-}(u), I_{A^-}(v)\}, \max^i\{I_{A^+}(u), I_{A^+}(v)\}]$$

$$= \max^i\{[I_{A^-}(u), I_{A^+}(u)], [I_{A^-}(v), I_{A^+}(v)]\}$$

$$= \max^i\{I_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{A}}(v)\}$$

$$F_{\bar{A}}(u - v) = [F_{A^-}(u - v), F_{A^+}(u - v)] \leq [\max^i\{F_{A^-}(u), F_{A^-}(v)\}, \max^i\{F_{A^+}(u), F_{A^+}(v)\}]$$

$$= \max^i\{[F_{A^-}(u), F_{A^+}(u)], [F_{A^-}(v), F_{A^+}(v)]\}$$

$$= \max^i\{F_{\bar{A}}(u), F_{\bar{A}}(v)\}$$

$$T_{\bar{A}}(uv) = [T_{A^-}(uv), T_{A^+}(uv)] \geq [\min^i\{T_{A^-}(u), T_{A^-}(v)\}, \min^i\{T_{A^+}(u), T_{A^+}(v)\}]$$

$$= \min^i\{[T_{A^-}(u), T_{A^+}(u)], [T_{A^-}(v), T_{A^+}(v)]\}$$

$$= \min^i\{T_{\bar{A}}(u), T_{\bar{A}}(v)\}$$

$$I_{\bar{A}}(uv) = [I_{A^-}(uv), I_{A^+}(uv)] \leq [\max^i\{I_{A^-}(u), I_{A^-}(v)\}, \max^i\{I_{A^+}(u), I_{A^+}(v)\}]$$

$$= \max^i\{[I_{A^-}(u), I_{A^+}(u)], [I_{A^-}(v), I_{A^+}(v)]\}$$

$$= \max^i\{I_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{A}}(v)\}$$

$$F_{\bar{A}}(uv) = [F_{A^-}(uv), F_{A^+}(uv)] \leq [\max^i\{F_{A^-}(u), F_{A^-}(v)\}, \max^i\{F_{A^+}(u), F_{A^+}(v)\}]$$

$$= \max^i\{[F_{A^-}(u), F_{A^+}(u)], [F_{A^-}(v), F_{A^+}(v)]\}$$

$$= \max^i\{F_{\bar{A}}(u), F_{\bar{A}}(v)\}$$

$$T_{\bar{A}}(v + u - v) = [T_{A^-}(v + u - v), T_{A^+}(v + u - v)] \geq [T_{A^-}(u), T_{A^+}(u)] = T_{\bar{A}}(u)$$

$$I_{\bar{A}}(v + u - v) = [I_{A^-}(v + u - v), I_{A^+}(v + u - v)] \leq [I_{A^-}(u), I_{A^+}(u)] = I_{\bar{A}}(u)$$

$$F_{\bar{A}}(v + u - v) = [F_{A^-}(v + u - v), F_{A^+}(v + u - v)] \leq [F_{A^-}(u), F_{A^+}(u)] = F_{\bar{A}}(u)$$

$$T_{\bar{A}}(uv) = [T_{A^-}(uv), T_{A^+}(uv)] \geq [T_{A^-}(v), T_{A^+}(v)] = T_{\bar{A}}(v)$$

$$I_{\bar{A}}(uv) = [I_{A^-}(uv), I_{A^+}(uv)] \leq [I_{A^-}(v), I_{A^+}(v)] = I_{\bar{A}}(v)$$

$$F_{\bar{A}}(uv) = [F_{A^-}(uv), F_{A^+}(uv)] \leq [F_{A^-}(v), F_{A^+}(v)] = F_{\bar{A}}(v)$$

$$T_{\bar{A}}((u + w)v - uv) = [T_{A^-}((u + w)v - uv), T_{A^+}((u + w)v - uv)] \geq [T_{A^-}(w), T_{A^+}(w)] = T_{\bar{A}}(w)$$

$$I_{\bar{A}}((u + w)v - uv) = [I_{A^-}((u + w)v - uv), I_{A^+}((u + w)v - uv)] \leq [I_{A^-}(w), I_{A^+}(w)] = I_{\bar{A}}(w)$$

$$F_{\bar{A}}((u + w)v - uv) = [F_{A^-}((u + w)v - uv), F_{A^+}((u + w)v - uv)] \leq [F_{A^-}(w), F_{A^+}(w)] = F_{\bar{A}}(w)$$

Definition 3.12 Let I is a subset in a near-ring R and $\bar{A}$ is an i-v neutrosophic fuzzy subset of R . Define $\bar{A} = \{\langle u, \chi_I(T_{\bar{A}}), \chi_I(I_{\bar{A}}), \chi_I(F_{\bar{A}}) \rangle \mid u \in R\}$, where $\chi_I(T_{\bar{A}}), \chi_I(I_{\bar{A}}), \chi_I(F_{\bar{A}}): R \rightarrow D[0,1]$ as follows

$$\chi_I(T_{\bar{A}})(u) = \begin{cases} \bar{1} & \text{if } u \in I \\ \bar{0} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$\chi_I(I_{\bar{A}})(u) = \begin{cases} \bar{0} & \text{if } u \in I \\ \bar{1} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$\chi_I(F_{\bar{A}})(u) = \begin{cases} \bar{0} & \text{if } u \in I \\ \bar{1} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Clearly $\chi_I(\bar{A})$ is an i-v neutrosophic subset of R . $\chi_I(\bar{A})$ is called the i-v neutrosophic characteristic function of I .

Theorem 3.13 Let I be a subset in a near-ring R . The characteristic function $\chi_I(\bar{A}): R \rightarrow D[0,1]$ is an i-v neutrosophic fuzzy left (resp. right) ideal of R if and only if I is a left (resp. right) ideal of R .

Proof. Let I be a left (resp. right) ideals of R . If

$$\begin{aligned}\chi_I(T_{\bar{A}})(u) &= \begin{cases} \bar{1} & \text{if } u \in I \\ \bar{0} & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \\ \chi_I(I_{\bar{A}})(u) &= \begin{cases} \bar{0} & \text{if } u \in I \\ \bar{1} & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \\ \chi_I(F_{\bar{A}})(u) &= \begin{cases} \bar{0} & \text{if } u \in I \\ \bar{1} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}\end{aligned}$$

Then $\chi_I(\bar{A})$ is an i-v neutrosophic fuzzy left (resp. right) ideal of R .

Conversely, assume that $\chi_I(\bar{A})$ is an i-v neutrosophic fuzzy left (resp. right) ideal of R . Let $u, v \in I$. Then

$$\chi_I(T_{\bar{A}})(u) = \bar{1} = \chi_I(T_{\bar{A}})(v), \chi_I(I_{\bar{A}})(u) = \bar{0} = \chi_I(I_{\bar{A}})(v), \chi_I(F_{\bar{A}})(u) = \bar{0} = \chi_I(F_{\bar{A}})(v). \text{ So,}$$

$$\chi_I(T_{\bar{A}})(u - v) \geq \min^i\{\chi_I(T_{\bar{A}})(u), \chi_I(T_{\bar{A}})(v)\} = \min^i\{\bar{1}, \bar{1}\} = \bar{1}$$

$$\chi_I(I_{\bar{A}})(u - v) \leq \max^i\{\chi_I(I_{\bar{A}})(u), \chi_I(I_{\bar{A}})(v)\} = \max^i\{\bar{0}, \bar{0}\} = \bar{0}$$

$$\chi_I(F_{\bar{A}})(u - v) \leq \max^i\{\chi_I(F_{\bar{A}})(u), \chi_I(F_{\bar{A}})(v)\} = \max^i\{\bar{0}, \bar{0}\} = \bar{0}$$

So, $\chi_I(T_{\bar{A}})(u - v) = \bar{1}, \chi_I(I_{\bar{A}})(u - v) = \bar{0}, \chi_I(F_{\bar{A}})(u - v) = \bar{0}$. Therefore $u - v \in I$. Hence I is an additive subgroup of R .

Let $u \in I$ and $v \in R$. Then

$$\chi_I(T_{\bar{A}})(uv) \geq \min^i\{\chi_I(T_{\bar{A}})(u), \chi_I(T_{\bar{A}})(v)\} = \min^i\{\bar{1}, \bar{1}\} = \bar{1}$$

$$\chi_I(I_{\bar{A}})(uv) \leq \max^i\{\chi_I(I_{\bar{A}})(u), \chi_I(I_{\bar{A}})(v)\} = \max^i\{\bar{0}, \bar{0}\} = \bar{0}$$

$$\chi_I(F_{\bar{A}})(uv) \leq \max^i\{\chi_I(F_{\bar{A}})(u), \chi_I(F_{\bar{A}})(v)\} = \max^i\{\bar{0}, \bar{0}\} = \bar{0}$$

Therefore $uv \in I$. Hence I is a multiplicative semigroup of R .

Let $u \in I$ and $v \in R$. Then

$$\chi_I(T_{\bar{A}})(v + u - v) \geq \{\chi_I(T_{\bar{A}})(u)\} = \bar{1}$$

$$\chi_I(I_{\bar{A}})(v + u - v) \leq \{\chi_I(I_{\bar{A}})(u)\} = \bar{0}$$

$$\chi_I(F_{\bar{A}})(v + u - v) \leq \{\chi_I(F_{\bar{A}})(u)\} = \bar{0}$$

Hence, $\chi_I(T_{\bar{A}})(v + u - v) = \bar{1}, \chi_I(I_{\bar{A}})(v + u - v) = \bar{0}, \chi_I(F_{\bar{A}})(v + u - v) = \bar{0}$. Which implies that $v + u - v \in I$, thus I is a normal subgroup of R .

Let $u \in R$ and $v \in I$. Then

$$\chi_I(T_{\bar{A}})(uv) \geq \{\chi_I(T_{\bar{A}})(v)\} = \bar{1}$$

$$\chi_I(I_{\bar{A}})(uv) \leq \{\chi_I(I_{\bar{A}})(v)\} = \bar{0}$$

$$\chi_I(F_{\bar{A}})(uv) \leq \{\chi_I(F_{\bar{A}})(v)\} = \bar{0}$$

Hence, $\chi_I(T_{\bar{A}})(uv) = \bar{1}, \chi_I(I_{\bar{A}})(uv) = \bar{0}, \chi_I(F_{\bar{A}})(uv) = \bar{0}$. Which implies that $uv \in I$ and I is a left ideal of R .

Let $u, v \in R$ and $w \in I$. Then

$$\chi_I(T_{\bar{A}})((u + w)u - uv) \geq \{\chi_I(T_{\bar{A}})(w)\} = \bar{1}$$

$$\chi_I(I_{\bar{A}})((u + w)u - uv) \leq \{\chi_I(I_{\bar{A}})(w)\} = \bar{0}$$

$$\chi_I(F_{\bar{A}})((u + w)u - uv) \leq \{\chi_I(F_{\bar{A}})(w)\} = \bar{0}$$

Hence, $\chi_I(T_{\bar{A}})((u + w)u - uv) = \bar{1}, \chi_I(I_{\bar{A}})((u + w)u - uv) = \bar{0}, \chi_I(F_{\bar{A}})((u + w)u - uv) = \bar{0}$, which implies that $((u + w)u - uv) \in I$

Thus I is a left (resp. right) ideal of R .

Definition 3.14 Let $\bar{A}$ be an i-v neutrosophic fuzzy subset of R . Then for any $[t_1, t_2] \in D[0, 1]$, then $[t_1, t_2]$ -upper level sets of $\bar{A}$ denoted by $\bar{U}(\bar{A}, [t_1, t_2])$ is defined as follows: $\bar{U}(\bar{A}, [t_1, t_2]) = \{u \in R | T_{\bar{A}}(u) \geq [t_1, t_2], I_{\bar{A}}(u) \leq [t_1, t_2], F_{\bar{A}}(u) \leq [t_1, t_2]\}$

Theorem 3.15 Let $\bar{A}$ be an i-v neutrosophic fuzzy subset of R . $\bar{A}$ is an i-v neutrosophic fuzzy left (resp. right) ideal of R if and only if $\bar{U}(\bar{A}; [t_1, t_2])$ is a left (resp. right) ideal of R for all $[t_1, t_2] \in D[0, 1]$.

Proof. Consider $\bar{A}$ is an i-v neutrosophic fuzzy left (resp. right) ideal of R . Let $[t_1, t_2] \in D[0, 1]$, such that $u, v \in \bar{U}(\bar{A}; [t_1, t_2])$. Then,

$$T_{\bar{A}}(u - v) \geq \min^i\{T_{\bar{A}}(u), T_{\bar{A}}(v)\} = \min^i\{[t_1, t_2], [t_1, t_2]\} = [t_1, t_2]$$

$$I_{\bar{A}}(u - v) \leq \max^i\{I_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{A}}(v)\} = \max^i\{[t_1, t_2], [t_1, t_2]\} = [t_1, t_2]$$

$$F_{\bar{A}}(u - v) \leq \max^i\{F_{\bar{A}}(u), F_{\bar{A}}(v)\} = \max^i\{[t_1, t_2], [t_1, t_2]\} = [t_1, t_2]$$

Thus, $(u - v) \in \bar{U}(\bar{A}; [t_1, t_2])$. Hence $\bar{U}(\bar{A}; [t_1, t_2])$ is an additive subgroup of R .

Let $u \in \bar{U}(\bar{A}; [t_1, t_2])$ and $v \in R$.

$$T_{\bar{A}}(uv) \geq \min^i\{T_{\bar{A}}(u), T_{\bar{A}}(v)\} = \min^i\{[t_1, t_2], [t_1, t_2]\} = [t_1, t_2]$$

$$I_{\bar{A}}(uv) \leq \max^i\{I_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{A}}(v)\} = \max^i\{[t_1, t_2], [t_1, t_2]\} = [t_1, t_2]$$

$$F_{\bar{A}}(uv) \leq \max^i\{F_{\bar{A}}(u), F_{\bar{A}}(v)\} = \max^i\{[t_1, t_2], [t_1, t_2]\} = [t_1, t_2]$$

Thus, $(uv) \in \bar{U}(\bar{A}; [t_1, t_2])$. Hence $\bar{U}(\bar{A}; [t_1, t_2])$ is a multiplicative semigroup of R .

Let $u \in \bar{U}(\bar{A}; [t_1, t_2])$ and $v \in R$.

$$T_{\bar{A}}(v + u - v) \geq T_{\bar{A}}(u) = [t_1, t_2]$$

$$I_{\bar{A}}(v + u - v) \leq I_{\bar{A}}(u) = [t_1, t_2]$$

$$F_{\bar{A}}(v + u - v) \leq F_{\bar{A}}(u) = [t_1, t_2]$$

Therefore, $(v + u - v) \in \bar{U}(\bar{A}: [t_1, t_2])$. Hence $\bar{U}(\bar{A}: [t_1, t_2])$ is a normal subgroup of R .

Let $v \in \bar{U}(\bar{A}: [t_1, t_2])$ and $u \in R$.

$$T_{\bar{A}}(uv) \geq T_{\bar{A}}(v) = [t_1, t_2], I_{\bar{A}}(uv) \leq I_{\bar{A}}(v) = [t_1, t_2], F_{\bar{A}}(uv) \leq F_{\bar{A}}(v) = [t_1, t_2]$$

Therefore, $(uv) \in \bar{U}(\bar{A}: [t_1, t_2])$.

Let $w \in \bar{U}(\bar{A}: [t_1, t_2])$ and $u, v \in R$.

$$T_{\bar{A}}((u + w)v - uv) \geq T_{\bar{A}}(w) = [t_1, t_2]$$

$$I_{\bar{A}}((u + w)v - uv) \leq I_{\bar{A}}(w) = [t_1, t_2]$$

$$F_{\bar{A}}((u + w)v - uv) \leq F_{\bar{A}}(w) = [t_1, t_2]$$

Therefore, $((u + w)v - uv) \in \bar{U}(\bar{A}: [t_1, t_2])$. Hence $\bar{U}(\bar{A}: [t_1, t_2])$ is left (resp. right) ideal of R .

Conversely, assume that $\bar{U}(\bar{A}: [t_1, t_2])$ is a left (resp. right) ideal of R , for all $[t_1, t_2] \in D[0, 1]$.

Let $u, v \in R$. Suppose, $T_{\bar{A}}(u - v) < \min^i\{T_{\bar{A}}(u), T_{\bar{A}}(v)\}$. Choose an interval $\bar{a} = [a_1, a_2] \in D[0, 1]$.

Such that, $T_{\bar{A}}(u - v) < [a_1, a_2] < \min^i\{T_{\bar{A}}(u), T_{\bar{A}}(v)\}$.

This implies that, $T_{\bar{A}}(u) > [a_1, a_2]$ and $T_{\bar{A}}(v) > [a_1, a_2]$.

Suppose, $I_{\bar{A}}(u - v) > \max^i\{I_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{A}}(v)\}$. Choose an interval $\bar{a} = [a_1, a_2] \in D[0, 1]$.

Such that, $I_{\bar{A}}(u - v) > [a_1, a_2] > \max^i\{I_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{A}}(v)\}$.

This implies that, $I_{\bar{A}}(u) < [a_1, a_2]$ and $I_{\bar{A}}(v) < [a_1, a_2]$.

Similarly, we can derive for $(F_{\bar{A}})$.

Then we have, $(u, v) \in \bar{U}(\bar{A}: [a_1, a_2])$ and since $\bar{U}(\bar{A}: [a_1, a_2])$ is a additive subgroup of R , $(u - v) \in \bar{U}(\bar{A}: [a_1, a_2])$. Hence, $T_{\bar{A}}(u - v) \geq [a_1, a_2]$, $I_{\bar{A}}(u - v) \leq [a_1, a_2]$, $F_{\bar{A}}(u - v) \leq [a_1, a_2]$, which is a contradiction. Thus,

$$T_{\bar{A}}(u - v) \geq \min^i\{T_{\bar{A}}(u), T_{\bar{A}}(v)\},$$

$$I_{\bar{A}}(u - v) \leq \max^i\{I_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{A}}(v)\},$$

$$F_{\bar{A}}(u - v) \leq \max^i\{F_{\bar{A}}(u), F_{\bar{A}}(v)\}.$$

Suppose, $T_{\bar{A}}(uv) < \min^i\{T_{\bar{A}}(u), T_{\bar{A}}(v)\}$. Choose an interval $\bar{a} = [a_1, a_2] \in D[0, 1]$.

Such that, $T_{\bar{A}}(uv) < [a_1, a_2] < \min^i\{T_{\bar{A}}(u), T_{\bar{A}}(v)\}$.

This implies that, $T_{\bar{A}}(u) > [a_1, a_2]$ and $T_{\bar{A}}(v) > [a_1, a_2]$.

Suppose, $I_{\bar{A}}(uv) > \max^i\{I_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{A}}(v)\}$. Choose an interval $\bar{a} = [a_1, a_2] \in D[0, 1]$.

Such that, $I_{\bar{A}}(uv) > [a_1, a_2] > \max^i\{I_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{A}}(v)\}$.

This implies that, $I_{\bar{A}}(u) < [a_1, a_2]$ and $I_{\bar{A}}(v) < [a_1, a_2]$.

Similarly, we can derive for $(F_{\bar{A}})$.

Then we have, $(u, v) \in \bar{U}(\bar{A}: [a_1, a_2])$ and since $\bar{U}(\bar{A}: [a_1, a_2])$ is a multiplicative semigroup of R , $(uv) \in \bar{U}(\bar{A}: [a_1, a_2])$. Hence, $T_{\bar{A}}(uv) \geq [a_1, a_2]$, $I_{\bar{A}}(uv) \leq [a_1, a_2]$, $F_{\bar{A}}(uv) \leq [a_1, a_2]$, which is a contradiction. Thus,

$$T_{\bar{A}}(uv) \geq \min^i\{T_{\bar{A}}(u), T_{\bar{A}}(v)\},$$

$$I_{\bar{A}}(uv) \leq \max^i\{I_{\bar{A}}(u), I_{\bar{A}}(v)\},$$

$$F_{\bar{A}}(uv) \leq \max^i\{F_{\bar{A}}(u), F_{\bar{A}}(v)\}.$$

Suppose, $T_{\bar{A}}(v + u - v) < T_{\bar{A}}(u)$. Choose an interval $\bar{a} = [a_1, a_2] \in D[0, 1]$.

Such that, $T_{\bar{A}}(v + u - v) < [a_1, a_2] < T_{\bar{A}}(u)$.

This implies that, $T_{\bar{A}}(u) > [a_1, a_2]$.

Suppose, $I_{\bar{A}}(v + u - v) > T_{\bar{A}}(u)$. Choose an interval $\bar{a} = [a_1, a_2] \in D[0, 1]$.

Such that, $I_{\bar{A}}(v + u - v) > [a_1, a_2] > I_{\bar{A}}(u)$.

This implies that, $I_{\bar{A}}(u) < [a_1, a_2]$.

Similarly, we can derive for $(F_{\bar{A}})$.

Then we have, $u \in \bar{U}(\bar{A}: [a_1, a_2])$ and since $\bar{U}(\bar{A}: [a_1, a_2])$ is a normal subgroup of $(R, +)$, $(v + u - v) \in \bar{U}(\bar{A}: [a_1, a_2])$. Hence, $T_{\bar{A}}(v + u - v) \geq [a_1, a_2]$, $I_{\bar{A}}(v + u - v) \leq [a_1, a_2]$, $F_{\bar{A}}(v + u - v) \leq [a_1, a_2]$, which is a contradiction. Thus,

$$T_{\bar{A}}(v + u - v) \geq T_{\bar{A}}(u),$$

$$I_{\bar{A}}(v + u - v) \leq T_{\bar{A}}(u),$$

$$F_{\bar{A}}(v + u - v) \leq T_{\bar{A}}(u).$$

Suppose, $T_{\bar{A}}(uv) < T_{\bar{A}}(v)$. Choose an interval $\bar{a} = [a_1, a_2] \in D[0, 1]$.

Such that, $T_{\bar{A}}(uv) < [a_1, a_2] < T_{\bar{A}}(v)$. This implies that, $T_{\bar{A}}(v) > [a_1, a_2]$.

Suppose, $I_{\bar{A}}(uv) > I_{\bar{A}}(v)$. Choose an interval $\bar{a} = [a_1, a_2] \in D[0, 1]$.

Such that, $I_{\bar{A}}(uv) > [a_1, a_2] > I_{\bar{A}}(v)$. This implies that, $I_{\bar{A}}(v) < [a_1, a_2]$.

Similarly, we can derive for $(F_{\bar{A}})$.

Then we have, $v \in \bar{U}(\bar{A}: [a_1, a_2])$ and since $\bar{U}(\bar{A}: [a_1, a_2])$ is a left (resp. right) ideal of R , $(uv) \in \bar{U}(\bar{A}: [a_1, a_2])$.

Hence, $T_{\bar{A}}(uv) \geq [a_1, a_2]$, $I_{\bar{A}}(uv) \leq [a_1, a_2]$, $F_{\bar{A}}(uv) \leq [a_1, a_2]$, which is a contradiction. Thus,

$$T_{\bar{A}}(uv) \geq T_{\bar{A}}(v),$$

$$\begin{aligned} I_{\bar{A}}(uv) &\leq I_{\bar{A}}(v), \\ F_{\bar{A}}(uv) &\leq F_{\bar{A}}(v). \end{aligned}$$

Suppose, $T_{\bar{A}}((u+w)v - uv) < T_{\bar{A}}(w)$. Choose an interval $\bar{a} = [a_1, a_2] \in D[0, 1]$.

Such that, $T_{\bar{A}}((u+w)v - uv) < [a_1, a_2] < T_{\bar{A}}(w)$. This implies that, $T_{\bar{A}}(w) > [a_1, a_2]$.

Suppose, $I_{\bar{A}}((u+w)v - uv) > I_{\bar{A}}(w)$. Choose an interval $\bar{a} = [a_1, a_2] \in D[0, 1]$.

Such that, $I_{\bar{A}}((u+w)v - uv) > [a_1, a_2] > I_{\bar{A}}(w)$. This implies that, $I_{\bar{A}}(w) < [a_1, a_2]$.

Similarly, we can derive for $(F_{\bar{A}})$.

Then we have, $w \in \bar{U}(\bar{A}: [a_1, a_2])$ and since $\bar{U}(\bar{A}: [a_1, a_2])$ is a left (resp. right) idea of R , $((u+w)v - uv) \in \bar{U}(\bar{A}: [a_1, a_2])$.

Hence, $T_{\bar{A}}((u+w)v - uv) \geq [a_1, a_2]$, $I_{\bar{A}}((u+w)v - uv) \leq [a_1, a_2]$, $F_{\bar{A}}((u+w)v - uv) \leq [a_1, a_2]$, which is a contradiction. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} T_{\bar{A}}((u+w)v - uv) &\geq T_{\bar{A}}(w), \\ I_{\bar{A}}((u+w)v - uv) &\leq I_{\bar{A}}(w), \\ F_{\bar{A}}((u+w)v - uv) &\leq F_{\bar{A}}(w). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\bar{A}$ is an i-v neutrosophic fuzzy left (resp. right) ideal of R .

4. Conclusion

This document explores the notion of subnear-rings within the framework of i-v neutrosophic fuzzy algebra and explores their properties. The study encompasses i-v neutrosophic fuzzy ideals within near-rings, investigating their algebraic characteristics. Demonstratively, we establish that the union of two i-v neutrosophic fuzzy ideals within a near-ring results in an i-v neutrosophic fuzzy ideal within that same near-ring. Showcasing its property as an i-v neutrosophic fuzzy ideal. Extending our findings, we illustrate the applicability of these results to a finite number of i-v neutrosophic fuzzy ideals within near-rings.

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